

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING OF ICT PROGRAMS IN TEACHING
TRANSLATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7482112>

D.K.Qodiraliyeva

masters degree student,

National University of Uzbekistan

Scientific adviser: PhD

R.O.Sotlikova

National University of Uzbekistan

Annotation: *Everyone is aware that translation is a human endeavor. The study's primary objective is to concentrate on the potential of ICT (Information and Communication Teaching) in the teaching of translation and establish a connection between computer behavior and human behavior in terms of ICT. The value of ICT is diminished when it comes to helping classroom activities and strengthening the abilities of translation beginners. This study also shows that the big theoretical predictions about ICT's potential are not always supported by the quality of educational tools, but the manner ICT is utilized may have the power to improve novices' technological skills. Additionally, it observes that ICT concentrated on using computerized programs of teaching and manage the text through the use of apps and software to recreate a sort of leaning simulation between human and machine translation.*

Key words: *ICT, translation, application, technology, translation pedagogy*

The reasons for using computers in translation didactics are manifold. Carrove (1999) points out and summarizes the main ones below: 1. Because computer-literacy and familiarity with computer-assisted tools software is becoming an integral part of the training of translators. 2. The entry of computers into all fields of knowledge has changed the way we work, study and even think. But if there is one area which has experienced a strong impact with the

incorporation of computers and languages, it is undoubtedly translation. 3. The eighties and nineties have witnessed the growing importance and usefulness of computers in the day - today work of professional translators. The most useful contribution to the translation made by computers in recent years has been the development of various software and applications which fall short of actual fully automated machine translation. Novice translators, on the other hand, should be familiar with the use of technology driven basics of translation, data banks and, of course, application – processing techniques. New didactic approach seems to be associated with ICT as the next logical step in the area of translation pedagogy, nearly two decades afterwards it is still very much a theoretical than a tangible reality. Many translation academics are still using traditional methods to teach their students. The traditional methods do have their validity and usefulness in the field of teaching translation, most academically minded programmers still do not require students to acquire any knowledge on computer skills, not even computer literacy. The results are in a mismatch between the translating skills that students have learned during their training and the expertise that the real market expects from them (Carrove, 1999; Erben, et al. 2009; Williams, 2013: 114). Carrove (1999) points out that one of the problems of novice translators is that they are untrained in computer assisted translation software, though they are users of apps and other software programs. They may embark on using such application in an easy way as long as they have good experience in usage. Translation training through computer assisted tools is a relatively lurching field in some academies, despite the fact that they may claim their use of new versions of software and modern methods of computer –assisted teaching. A tremendous amount of work has been done on machine translation programs and the use of computers to learn foreign languages, very little work has been done on finding methods of teaching students to become translators ready to face an ever competitive field.

What Makes Teaching Translation a New Technology? In teaching and learning, as in many other aspects of life, is usually effected by innovations, new

technologies have an essential role to play, and can facilitate many of the tasks involved. Teaching classrooms have essentially been associated with the structure of modern era of technology. Some skeptics have referred that there are however some risks relatively in teaching aided by technological innovation such as atrophy of human intellectual innovation and creativity. An approach adopted by many institutions witnessed in their mission or policy statements. It considered that innovation in teaching practice have been aided by technology in mandatory to develop students skills and creative abilities in the field of research and profession.

First Application of New Technology: Biggs (2003: 214) points out that the use of information technology for teaching may even heighten the risk of returning or maintaining purely transmission. Putting lecture notes on an internet may seem innovative, but does not in fact enhance learning in any way; it simply facilitates access to information. Hence, scholars may prefer to use the term education technology in an attempt to remind teachers that overall aim should enhance learning, not simply to give information. The translation pedagogy, the issue of new technologies is of course not only a question of using new technologies for teaching and learning, but also helping students to learn how to use new technologies as applied to translation. Biggs (2003:214) identifies four main areas: managing learning, engaging learners, in an appropriate learning activity, assessing learning and distance or off campus teaching. New technologies can also prove to be of enormous help to teachers and trainers in managing teaching and learning activities in general. Web technology and e mail contacts electronic classes clearly facilitate tasks such as record keeping, lists, providing information for students (see Zenettin, 2012; Erben, et al. 2009). Probably more importantly, they facilitate communication between teachers and students, among teachers and among students. A common complaint among teaching staff is that an e mail communication has increased their Workload, as students now find it easier to ask more questions., make more direct requests, and also expect immediate replies. The up-side of this is that greater and easier communication between students and

teachers is undoubtedly a good thing for better learning (Zenettin, 2012; Erben, et al. 2009). The down-side is that, in effect, authorities often interpret new technologies as a cheap way of dealing with larger groups, and neglect to take into account the very real extent to which staff time is being taken up by their use. Kelly (2005:86) developed the mechanism of dealing with the new workload, they are as follows: 1. Pre prepared replies to frequent questions (which can also be included on the module website or electronic bulletin board as FAQ. 2. Encourage peer consultation through e mail groups and forums. 3. Explaining email etiquette to students (use of re line to indicate module and subject matter clearly, short concise messages, reading all relevant material on paper or on the website before writing with question, as the answer is already available, waiting a reasonable period of time for reply and so on).

Information and computer teaching ICT for task-based should aim to bring about intensive learner involvement and motivation, and should confront the learner with relevant tasks that give rise to the meaningful exchange and relevant focus on form. The application of ICT can be analyzed through the following variables: 1. ICT teaching is interesting and relevant to the translation training within the academic standards. 2. The application of ICT is not only potential in language learning rather it is highly influential in developing computer skills. 3. It develops interactive capabilities in classroom evaluation. 4. Tasks are authentic at the level of content and with regard to the interactional and the cognitive processes involved. 5. Multimedia offer multi-sensory support. 6. The learner is in control of interactive process.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Biggs, J. (2003). Teaching for quality learning at university. What the student does. Maidenhead. Open University Press
2. Carrove, M. (1999). Towards a theory of translation Pedagogy. Doctoral thesis dissertation. Department of English and Linguistics Universitat de Lleida Erbaen, T.
3. Ban, R. and Castañeda, M. (2009). Teaching English Language Learners through technology. Routledge: London
4. Kelly, D. (2005). A Handbook for Translator and Trainers. St. Jerome. Manchester
5. Schrooten, W. (1997). Task-based language teaching and ICT: developing and assessing interactive multimedia for taskbased language teaching. Speigal, 15/3, 16-81.
6. Williams, J. (2013). The Palgrave Macmillan: Theories of Translation. Palgrave Macmillan: London Zenettin, F. (2012). Translation – Driven Corpora. Corpus – Based Descriptive Translation Studies. Routledge: London